

Effect of School-Affinity regarding Teacher's Personality and Profile on the Academic Achievement of Students at Secondary Level

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Abstract

This study determine the effect of school-affinity regarding Teacher's Personality and Profile on the Academic Achievement of Students at Secondary Level in Punjab, Pakistan. Data was collected by administering 10 items agree-disagree type questionnaire to the randomly selected 8000 students from 1040 secondary schools. Multistage random sampling is used for the representation. Factor of school affinity, teachers' personality and profile (behaviour) is the main sub-variable of the study. The academic achievement of the students was determined on the base of Annual Results of 9th class students. Accumulative mean scores of students' response show the prevalence of higher level of affinity with teacher's personality and profile. Similarly, Pearson Correlation Coefficients demonstrates significant effect with school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile on the academic achievement of students.

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Introduction

School is a place of love for the social, intellectual, behavioral and emotional development for the child. Therefore, the concept of affinity (like) for school is used as a phrase with the term "school-affinity" (Shabbir et al., 2020). Affinity is "a natural liking for or attraction of a person (not a blood relationship) or a liking for a thing or idea" (World English Dictionary). The word affinity was first time introduced by McCroskey and Wheelless in 1976. In 1977, affinity is used as an affinity-group in the United States. Affinity-groups are the small groups organized by common ideology, shared common issues of individuals, shared attributes, or beliefs (Michael & Conger, 2009; Shookhoff, 2006). The study of McCroskey and Wheelless addresses the basic function of affinity as a human communication. People struggle to obtain knowledge and skills actively known some societal behaviors to increase liking toward them and develops affinity from others. After them many researchers of communication have deliberate such societal behavior that people communicate strategies during interpersonal communication. After McCroskey and Wheelless, Bell and Daly in 1984 used another phrase of affinity-seeking which is defined as the "active social communicative process by which people effort to get others to like and to feel positive toward them." The study of McCroskey and McCroskey in 1986 constructs affinity in the field of education by using the original typology of Bell and Daly (1984) at elementary and secondary level. They analyze the level of affinity seeking strategy practice to take on Bell and Daly (1984) original typology to the teacher-student relationship. The relationship of the teacher's personality and student is more interpersonal due to spending more time together in school. This relationship construct affinity to school and students perform better in the classroom that effect on the academic achievement of student. Gorham, Kelly and McCroskey's (1989) research study was related to the teacher and subject matter by the use of frequency of affinity seeking techniques. Result shows that the usage of affinity seeking techniques in the classroom improves the students' academic achievement.

Teaching is the process which develops students intelligent during education in school in respect of their capacity (Karsli, 2007: 17). The most important factor of school in teaching activities is the teacher. In general, a teacher is a person working in school that gives knowledge and skills to students to achieve the desired domain of development and covers the syllabus of their class determined by the school (Gundogdu, Silman, 2007: 259). Temel (1988: 21) has suggested that teacher play a vital role in developing the society, creating a sound basis towards the future of society and ensuring the continuance of such work. In the era of modern technology, the best definition of teacher has gone beyond just teaching students, delivering lectures, paper marking and grading; the teacher also play an important roles for organizing, directing, managing, counseling, observing and evaluating the whole system of an institute.

According to Can & Inelmen (2011), school is the first fundamental socialization place for the students, after the home. Apart from the home, it's the teacher's personality and profile who is effectively in the front seat in regards to student's personality development in both curricular and co-curricular activities. The understanding of technology based education in present day, the role of teacher in respect of duty and responsibility is very effective. The responsibility of character building and intellectual development of a student is on the shoulders of the teacher. This is only possible that teacher's personality and profile being able to develop healthy personality of students as well as providing efficiency in their relationships with them so as to allow them to develop their attachment with school.

The abilities and characteristics of a good teacher having good personality and profile are also the same features that represent a good education. The basic characteristics of good teacher's personality and profile are; subject matter knowledge, good decision; critical thinking and ability of problem solving; self correction and understanding; reflecting; identifying students and knowing students learning requirements; follow new finding and strategies in education; Teaching and communication skills. We can collect these data under two headings (Ari, 2008: 5 - 6). The teacher's critically thinking and the self-governing teacher. A teacher who think that the nature of subject matter knowledge and behavior directly affects his/her students and community acquire task for his/her own knowledge and skill, develops positive involvement with his/her students and can communicate these to students in the most proficient way (Ari, 2008: 5 - 6).

In this complete process, the effect of the teacher's personality and behavior in respect of personality development and academic achievement of students is a reality that cannot be ignored. The teacher, through both positive or negative personality and profile in discussion with students and what will be the result? Gives the way of their lives, has a positive or negative effect on the approach shown toward students or the public in general, affecting to develop self-confidence in students creating the ability of communication, innovation and creativity which attach the students with school (Ataunal, 2003). The personality and behaviour of the teacher is directly acknowledged and imitative by students, which lays great tasks on the teachers. For a teacher, being able to engage with the student and show positive behavior like inquire questions, inspiring their opinion, like their interest and appreciation increases the students' attachment with school and their academic achievement. When a teacher provides information, experience and behavior to the students on a certain topic, students copied teachers as a role model by adopting their own behavior and attitude. Teacher's positive personality and profile lead to academic success while negative personality and profile lead to academic failure and as a result academic success can lead to positive ego profile while failure leads to negative ego profile. Such as, if the teacher addresses in disparagement remarks towards a student due to his/her failure, the negative effects of this will be predictable (Gecer, 2002).

The students' academic achievement is not totally the result of their effort; academic achievement is affected by many factors and one of the most top is the personality and profile of a teacher. A positive personality and profile from the teacher affects the student's motivation, behavior towards school and school attachment, the student's self confidence and as a result academic achievement (Shabbir et al., 2021).

In the system of education, communication process is also an important factor of a good teacher's personality and profile. The teacher, who tries to understand students' emotions such as interest, anxiety, and worry, helps students' learning activities, aspirates, support of and greetings them for activities he/she thinks of value will make the students feel that they are being thought of, loved and aided, and that the teacher is working for their good that develop attachment with school. Students of such a teacher will, taking the teacher as a role model make causes their attachment with school, in turn be thoughtful of others, organization to the aid of others, establish good relations and positive behaviour (Basaran, 1994).

In this study, it is expected that students whose teachers have good personality and profile will state that there is effect of school-affinity on the academic achievement of secondary school students. The uniqueness of this study is that earlier studies focused on two variables but in this study the researcher used three variables instead of two which is considered as a factor of school-affinity that are interrelated with each others. Second noticeable gap is that the independent variable (school-affinity) of this present study varies considerably from the earlier studies. Third identified gap that warranted this study is that the locale of this present study varies considerably from the locale of earlier studies. Due to this background, researcher was conducted this study under the title, "effect of school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile on the academic achievement of students at secondary level."

Objectives of the study:

1. To understand the insights and aspects of school affinity at secondary school level.
2. To analyze the effect of school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile on the academic achievement of students.

Research Questions:

1. What are insights and aspects of school affinity at secondary school level?

2. What is the effect of school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile on the academic achievement of students?

Research Hypothesis:

H0: School-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile has no significant effect on the academic achievement of students.

Research Methodology:

The research design of this study was descriptive in nature. All the students of secondary school of Punjab were the population of this study. The reasons for choosing of this level of students as participants is that they are in the best position to develop school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile. The target population of this research was comprised of all the students of 10th class who had passed the 9th class annual examination of secondary school education in 2020 conducted by all the boards of intermediate and secondary education (BISE_s) of 130 tehsil of 36 districts of Punjab in Pakistan. However, for the purpose of this study, multistage sample technique for 1040 secondary schools and 8,000 students of secondary school was used as a sample. All the districts (36) of Punjab, 130 tehsil were selected randomly. From each tehsil eight (8) schools were selected conveniently. Ten (10) students from each school were selected randomly. A tool (questionnaire) of school-affinity scale (SAS) with the four-point likert scale of strongly disagreed to strongly agreed was developed in this study to collect data from those students who had passed the 9th class annual examination conducted by all the boards of intermediate and secondary education (BISE_s) of Punjab. The school-affinity scale (SAS) was constructed with the sub-variable of teacher's personality and profile while the SAS was used to collect the annual result of 9th class conducted by all the boards of intermediate and secondary education (BISE_s) for data collection. After the finalization of a validated research tool by the experts of Education Faculty, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, next step of this scale was to check its reliability. For this purpose a pilot testing of the instrument was developed to check the level of school-affinity. A standardized procedure was used to develop the instrument of SAS. The SAS showed the Cronbach alpha coefficient was .851 and for sub-variables it ranged from .86 to .73. These significant values showed the highly reliability and internally consistency of the scale. The researcher administered the questionnaire personally to assess the level of school-affinity to the students from a larger sample within limited time. The researcher administered 10400 questionnaire among the students and their return rate was hundred percent. However, twenty three percent incomplete questionnaires were excluded after scrutiny when the data was in the stage of reviewing and cleaning process. Thus, 8000 participants of secondary school students were considered suitable for analyzing the collected data. The collected data were analyzed through SPSS version 21 by using the frequencies, mean, t-test and Pearson correlation coefficient at the significant level of 0.05.

Table 1 Statements of students' response showing school-affinity regarding teachers' personality and profile

Sr #	Statement	Disagree Frequency	Disagree Percentage	Agree Frequency	Agree Percentage
1	My teachers know how to impart knowledge even to the slow-learners	1495	18.7	6505	81.3
2	My teachers are well-versed with the communication skills.	1512	18.9	6188	81.1
3	Good management of our classroom is a natural result of good teaching.	1476	18.5	6524	81.6
4	My class teachers maintain discipline in a democratic way.	1503	18.8	6497	81.2
5	Students follow the instructions of sympathetic class teachers willingly.	1521	19.0	6479	81.0
6	Our teachers are also good class-managers.	1474	18.4	6526	81.6
7	My teachers appreciate students, showing good performance	1516	19.0	6484	81.0

8	I find my teachers, ready to solve students' problems.	1484	18.6	6511	81.4
9	My teachers come prepared in the class.	1467	18.3	6533	81.7
10	My teachers make use of novel strategies to motivate students for learning	1450	18.1	6550	81.9
Accumulative Mean Score		3.25			

Table 1 reveals that 18.3 % of participant at secondary level in the sample disagree with the statement that their teachers know how to impart knowledge even to the slow-learners whereas 81.7 % of the participants agree with this statement. Similarly, 18.9 % of the secondary school participants in the sample also disagree with the statement that their teachers are well-versed with the communication skills whereas 81.1 % of the participants agree with this statement. The table shows that 18.5 % of the participants in the sample give their dissent with the statement that good management of their classroom is a natural result of good teaching whereas 81.5 % of the participants agree with this statement. It demonstrates that 18.8 % of the participants of secondary school in the sample deny the idea of discipline that their class teachers maintain discipline in a democratic way whereas 81.2 % of the participants accept the idea of this statement. The data explains that 19 % of the participants in the sample disagree with the statement that students follow the instructions of sympathetic class teachers willingly whereas 81 % of the participants believe the concept of this statement. It reveals that 18.4 % of the participants in the sample oppose with the statement that their teachers are also good class-managers whereas 81.6 % of the participants agree with this statement. Data shows that 19 % of the students of secondary school in the sample reject the statement that their teachers appreciate students, showing good performance whereas 81 % of the participants agree to this idea. The table also displays that 18.6 % of the students of secondary school in the sample refuse the idea of the statement that they find their teachers, ready to solve students' problems whereas 81.4% of the participants believe the idea of this statement. The statement also reveals the teachers' preparation that 18.3 % of the participants of secondary school in the sample reject this thought that their teachers come prepared in the class whereas 81.7 % of the students believe the idea of this statement. The table explores the teaching strategies that 18.1% of the secondary school participants in the sample reject with the statement that their teachers make use of novel strategies to motivate students for learning whereas 81.9% of the participants believe the idea of this statement. This table shows that accumulative mean score of 3.25 demonstrates the prevalence of higher level of school-affinity effect regarding teacher's personality and profile among the participants.

Table 2 *Effect of school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile on the academic achievement of students in respect of Pearson Correlation Coefficients*

Effect of school-affinity	Academic Achievement	Sig.
Teacher's personality and profile	.100**	.000

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 demonstrates that the Pearson Correlation Coefficient's value is .000 which is significant at the level of 0.01. It illustrates that the academic achievements of secondary school students are directly correlated with school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile.

Findings:

In this study the hypothesis was tested on the base of Pearson Correlation Coefficients. Findings demonstrates that school-affinity have a higher level of positive relationship with the academic achievement of students in the sub-variable of teacher's personality and profile. The value of Pearson Correlation Coefficients .000 was less than the significant value of 0.01 which indicates that the hypothesis is rejected. It was analyzed that effect of school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile were significantly related with the academic achievement of secondary school students of Punjab.

Conclusion:

This study aim is to determine the effect of school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and academic achievement of secondary school students in Punjab. The main task is to determine the effect of school-affinity on the basis of sub-variable teacher's personality and profile on the academic achievement of students at secondary level. The objective of the study is to determine the effect of school-affinity regarding teacher's personality and profile on the academic achievement of students at secondary level. Initial stage of the findings indicates accumulative mean score regarding teachers' personality and profile on the academic achievement

students. Responses of the participants 3.23 indicates prevalence of higher level of school-affinity regarding teachers' personality and profile. Similarly, on the basis of Pearson Correlation Coefficient, there is a significant effect on the teacher' personality and profile on the academic achievement of students. Polk's (2006) research shows related look about the teachers' personality and profile and high effectiveness of teachers displays certain personality traits which make use of novel strategies in instructional quality that influence on the academic achievement of students. Other researchers like Sikora, (1997); Umoren&Ogbodo (2001); Liard (2002); Dunn (2000) found similar views about the teachers' personality and their profile which indicates the fact that in teaching learning process, meaningful learning will take place only when a teacher creates such environment in which students feel comfortable to think new ideas and are not threatened by factors of school.

Discussion:

Findings of the study show that while teacher's personality and profile have significant effects on the students' academic achievement and construct affinity to school. This in turn obviously shows that in school only teacher improves the boundaries of the classroom in students' educational lives and determine the way how effective they can be throughout the life of the individual. After parents, School-affinity in respect of teachers is the second-highest determining variable in the development of students.

It must not be forgotten that students obtain on role models while learning and that is why may be the personality and profile of teachers, which they mostly spend their time with apart from their parents, has an specific affiliation with their school which do not depend upon their success or failure. Teachers being good role models should lead classes because their observation on life and behavior direct the student. In short, education is the tool of student's understanding which gives the student confidence, questions him/her and reveals him/her responsibility and how to perform pleasantly.

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